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Commentary on Ceccherini et al. (2022)

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Abstract

We generally appreciate the position of Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. (2022) that ground truth and remotely sensed data need to be combined to achieve reliable estimates. However, Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. (2022) make several incorrect and unfounded claims and accusations about Breidenbach, Ellison et al. (2022). We think these claims should be corrected. We respond to each of three basic *claims* by Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. (2022). Due to space limitations, we have focused on what we consider the principal points.

Keywords: Global Forest Watch, Landsat, Remote Sensing, National Forest Inventory, Greenhouse Gas Inventory

Response to claim (1)

“Increased sensitivity of the GFC product after 2015. [...] Breidenbach et al. are not bringing any new element to what has been discussed in Nature Matters Arising (Ceccherini et al. 2021)” (Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. 2022).

First, none of the previous *Matters Arising* comments (Palahí, Valbuena et al. 2021; Wernick, Ciais et al. 2021) attempted any validation of the Global Forest Change (GFC) data and were thus only able to hypothesize about possible causes of data discrepancies. Our analysis provides a fundamental contribution to the debate because it decisively illustrates, based on ground truth data, that the GFC data output cannot accurately represent change in harvested area and requires extensive validation. In the Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. (2021) Reply to the *Matters Arising* critiques, a sampling-based

46 approach is used to correct for inconsistencies in GFC data. Their approach, however, is flawed as will
47 be described in the next section.

48 Second, in an attempt to correct for the erroneous results in Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. (2020), the
49 Breidenbach, Ellison et al. (2022) paper was first submitted as a Matters Arising comment to Nature
50 in January 2021. The code and data used were made public on the 21st of March, 2021 (Breidenbach,
51 Ellison et al. 2021), so that Ceccherini et al., could verify our critique. After months of waiting, the
52 Nature editors elected not to publish our comment. So, we published an open preprint on the 6th of
53 April, 2021 (Breidenbach, Ellison et al. 2021). The Matters Arising Reply (Ceccherini, Duveiller et al.
54 2021) was published on the 28th of April, 2021, several months after our objections had been made
55 known to Ceccherini et al., and several weeks after our objections had been openly published.

56 The following claim is therefore incorrect:

57 “The impact of [... the change in the GFC algorithm] on harvest
58 statistics has been assessed and reported for the first
59 time in our rebuttal and accompanying documents” (Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. 2022).

60 Response to claim (2)

61 *“Circularity in sample-based validation due to Landsat*
62 *data. [...] The visual assessment of Landsat-derived NDVI*
63 *time series was used only to attribute to a specific year*
64 *the harvest [... The] increased sensitivity of the GFC*
65 *algorithm clearly did not affect the validation”* (Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. 2022).
66

67 We are well aware that the Landsat data were only used to determine the timing of changes
68 (harvest) in observed aerial images. However, the original Landsat images were *not* used for this
69 purpose. Instead, Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. (2021) used a Landsat-based image mosaic. Due to
70 dense cloud cover, the actual change (harvest) year can be incorrect, due to interpolation. Mosaic
71 images also frequently contain other adjustments, such as color alignments, etc., that can modify the
72 original data. Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. (2022) claim the GFC algorithm causes this problem and not
73 the data. However, this is just a *claim* that remains to be demonstrated.

74 Furthermore, the GFW providers themselves clearly highlighted their concerns about the need for
75 data validation, stating;

76 “It must also be noted that a full validation of the results incorporating Landsat 8 has not been
77 undertaken. Such an analysis may reveal a more sensitive ability to detect and map forest
78 disturbance with Landsat 8 data. If this is the case then there will be a more fundamental limitation
79 to the consistency of the mapped interannual loss before and after the inclusion of Landsat 8 data,
80 and a validation of Landsat 8-incorporated loss detection is planned.” (UMD 2015).

81 This statement clearly highlights that there are likely inconsistencies in the data itself, and not (only)
82 in the GFC algorithm. Further, we are convinced it is not good practice to use Landsat in any form to
83 validate a Landsat-based product (such as the GFC data output).

84 Response to claim (3)

85 *“Inconsistencies between remote sensing and NFIs validation. [...]*
86 *in the following paragraphs, we demonstrate*
87 *that these shortcomings [of Breidenbach et al. 2022] are undermining the validity of*
88 *the validation exercise presented, to the point that the*
89 *results cannot be considered as a reference for the evaluation*

90 of other studies” (Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. 2022).

91 We disagree with this claim based on answers to specific claims below.

92

93 “Notably, also Breidenbach et al. (2022), in the very last
94 paragraph of the [Appendix](#), consider their approach nonoptimal
95 for estimating actual harvested area” (Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. 2022).

96 The aim of Breidenbach, Ellison et al. (2022) was to understand why Ceccherini, Duveiller et al.
97 (2020) had come up with such erroneous estimates of increases in harvested area in Finland and
98 Sweden. Official harvest statistics already exist in Finland and Sweden. We had no desire to repeat
99 these statistics. Further, demonstrations of how to correctly combine and use NFI and remote
100 sensing data likewise already exist (e.g. McRoberts, Wendt et al. 2002; McRoberts, Vibrans et al.
101 2016; Breidenbach, Ivanovs et al. 2021). Such methodologies can also easily be applied to the
102 estimation of harvested area.

103

104 “*Difficulty in assessing commission errors.* The analysis
105 presented by Breidenbach et al. (2022), as stated also
106 by the authors, does not allow a full assessment of the
107 commission error on the harvest statistics (areas where
108 GFC assumes a harvest event that is not confirmed)” (Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. 2022).

109

110 Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. (2022) seem to believe, the Breidenbach, Ellison et al. (2022) approach
111 would not be able to handle commission error. We refer to the caption of Fig. 2 in Breidenbach,
112 Ellison et al. (2022) where the time series indicated in yellow is “no loss recorded in the field =
113 commission error”. This claim by Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. (2022) is thus clearly wrong.

114

115

116 “Despite [... a] sharp reduction in the sampling during the 2016–2018 period,
117 the uncertainty range for final felling in Fig. 1 in Breidenbach
118 et al. (2022) remains identical to the previous years,
119 while we expect them to increase” (Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. 2022).

120 This is yet another undocumented claim by (Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. 2022). First, the confidence
121 intervals in Fig. 1 in Breidenbach, Ellison et al. (2022) are clearly larger towards the end of the period.
122 Second, the *increase* in the confidence interval may be smaller than Ceccherini et al., expect. But, the
123 estimates in Fig. 1 are ratios with an estimated variance provided by an estimator (Equation (9)) in
124 Breidenbach, Ellison et al. (2022). Further, both these estimator equations and the data itself have
125 been available to Ceccherini et al. since March 2021 (as noted above). If anyone can point us to an
126 error in our calculations, we would be happy to provide a correction.

127

128 “*Difficulty to have an appropriate a priori stratified*
129 *sampling.* The spatial sampling of NFIs based on permanent
130 plots cannot be stratified a priori by stable forest
131 and harvest classes as recommended in sample-based
132 validation schemes (Olofsson et al. 2014; GFOI 2016)” (Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. 2022).

133

134 Stratified sampling schemes increase the efficiency of the estimators, since less reference data is
135 needed to obtain adequately precise estimates. However, due to the comparatively large number of

136 observations, NFIs are also capable of yielding adequate precision even though they are not made-
137 for-purpose, as demonstrated, for example in Breidenbach, Ellison et al. (2022). Further, although
138 stratification is often a wise strategy, it is not a requirement for validating GFC or any other remote
139 sensing data output.

140

141 *“Difficulty in the temporal attribution of loss year.*
142 Given the uncertainty related to the periodic sampling
143 of ground data (5 years interval) combined with that
144 of the GFC classification, the temporal attribution of
145 the management operation is different between NFIs
146 surveys and GFC. For this reason, Breidenbach et al.
147 (2022) forced the loss year of the NFIs plot with GFC
148 data where the latter were available, introducing a considerable
149 uncertainty in the process” (Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. 2022).

150 If anything, our methodology results in a more favorable assessment of the GFC accuracy by
151 Breidenbach, Ellison et al. (2022) and improves the overall accuracy of NFI assessments. Therefore,
152 we do not agree that we have introduced increased “uncertainty”.

153

154 “Second, Breidenbach
155 et al. (2022) recognize that NFIs use “stand-level
156 observations around the sample plots for area estimation
157 rather than only plot-level measurements,” leading to a
158 clear spatial mismatch between satellite retrievals and
159 the ground truth” (Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. 2022).

160 Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. (2022) have deleted the context for this citation, leaving a false impression
161 about what we intended to say. The complete sentence is the following;

162 “Second, official NFI statistics include measurements from both permanent and temporary sample
163 plots and utilize stand-level observations around the sample plots for area estimation rather than
164 only plot-level measurements.” (Breidenbach, Ellison et al. 2022)

165 In other words, the official statistics use stand-level observations because they reach acceptable
166 levels of accuracy and do not require satellite data support. Breidenbach, Ellison et al. (2022) did not
167 compare stand-level observations to GFC. This is a clear misrepresentation of what we have done.

168

169 Though more claims in Ceccherini, Duveiller et al. (2022) could easily be rebutted, due to space
170 limitations, we have focused on what we consider the principal points.

171

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